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Methods for Determining Biosocompatible Metal Alloys for the Prevention of Elvanoses in Persons Residing in Ecological Unfavorable Conditions

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Abstract

We know that at an orthopedic dental appointment, people using metal dentures show intolerance to structural materials, galvanoses, toxic stomatitis and delayed contact allergic reactions in the form of inflammatory phenomena in the areas where the metal parts of the prostheses adjoin the oral cavity (OC). At the same time, patients complain of a metallic taste, burning and pinching of the tongue, distortion of taste sensitivity, a feeling of various tastes. Often there are headaches, dizziness, weakness, fatigue, nausea, vomiting, digestive upset, sleep disturbance, heart pain [3,4].

Keywords: structural materials, galvanoses, toxic stomatitis, allergic reactions, metallic taste.

I. Introduction

To determine the biocompatibility of metal alloys obtained by optimal technological blanks; cast bar stock Ø12mm or pellets Ø2-6mm, cobalt-chrome alloy type KXS, using the Lira-100 portable expert diagnostic system, which allows improving the methodology for detecting and preventing the occurrence of OC galvanoses, as well as studying compensatory-adaptation changes in OC.

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Upon receipt of traditional blanks for casting KHS alloys in the form of rods, the main technological stages consisted of such main stages as melting, sandblasting, tumbling and cutting of rods into measuring parts. In this case, mechanical impact on structural alloys occurs. To obtain granules, we used a vacuum installation for pellet melting Indutherm (Germany) and all the technological process for melting, we made only small granules. To investigate the structure of cast semi-finished products, we used metallographic studies: corresponding to the methods of analysis. The composition of the studied alloys was determined by the method of micro X-ray spectral analysis.

II. Main part

The reactions of OC tissues to the patient and the sample were evaluated using the Lira-100bt expert diagnostic complex developed and manufactured in Russia, which meets the requirements of GOST 19687-89, GOST R 50444-92, technical specifications TU 9442-001-41971715-2007, 66 series, OGRNIP 305667405300010.

A total of 103 patients (53 women 50 men from 39 to 63 years old), wearing metal prostheses of various designs, 59 patients wearing metal prostheses cast from 44 granules wearing metal prostheses that had not been diagnosed with galvanosis were examined OC. The study was carried out by comparing the values of the coefficient of functional asymmetry of the initial measurement and the coefficient of functional asymmetry obtained by measuring with the studied sample. The coefficients are calculated using the software of the expert diagnostic complex "Lira-100", which is used to analyze changes in the parameters of the biological tissue electric reactivity (BTER), which is determined by the electro-reactivity [1, 2]. In order to study the content, reduced glutathione and the activity of glutathione-dependent enzymes of the pancreas at various degrees of secondary adentia in patients, we divided the clinical group I (group 1-3 teeth) in the case of defect replacement with whole-cast bridges (group IV). Comparison groups for V (clasp) and VI (laminar dentures) groups were II (absence of 4-10 teeth) and III (complete adentia) clinical groups, respectively.

In order to study the effect of pH-saliva on dentures in patients, it was carried out using a "pH-410" pH meter-millivoltmeter during the initial examination on the day the structures were fixed and after 6 months. The electrochemical potentials of metal inclusions in the OC were measured using the Universal Ionomer EV-74 device [5,7].

Observing the patients, a clinical assessment of manufactured prostheses was carried out according to modified basic criteria [6,7]. The condition of dentures in the examined patients was evaluated after the manufacture of new dentures and after 6 months.

To assess the secretory immunity received oral fluid (OF), which was a mixed saliva. In OF, the concentration of lactoferrin (Lf) and secretory immunoglobulin A (IG A) was determined by the solid-phase heterogeneous enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using "The Vector-Best" test systems. In order to assess the nonspecific resistance of MMOC, the adsorption reaction of microorganisms by buccal epithelial cells was used [7,8].

The amount of the year-old for the use of metal in traditional technology is 45-50%, with losses of metal 18-20%, the granulation technology allows you to get up to 80-90% of suitable metal, with losses = 1.5% , hanging from bar stocks of Ø12mm – 12.0-15.0g. Melting time of 50 grams of blanks in the form of bar stocks is on average 190 ± 2 sec., at 100 ± 2 sec.

III. Conclusion

Studies have shown the obvious advantages of producing cobalt and chromium alloys in the form of granules. A new form of release of KXS alloy in the form of granules allows it to be successfully used in individuals with adverse environmental factors.

KXS alloy with the production of performs in the form of granules is one of the structural materials that allow it to be used as a means of preventing complications when using metallic inclusions in people employed in metallurgical production.

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